
EFFECT OF PROBIOTIC APPLICATION ON GROWTH PERFORMANCE OF ASIAN
CATFISH (*Pangasius djambal*) LARVAE

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this experiment was to know the effect of different periods for probiotic application on growth performance of Asian catfish. Used as treatment was probiotic application: (A) started at 3 days after stocking; (B) started at 5 days after stocking; (C) started at 7 days after stocking; and (D) without any probiotic application as control with three replicates, respectively. Larvae were reared in 9 aquaria by dimension 95 x 45 x 45 cm³ filled with 100 liters of water. Sampling was taken every 7 days and the experiment was conducted for 35 days. The total body length, specific growth rate, and daily growth rate were measured during the experiment. The results showed that at the final body length of treatment C showed significantly difference ($P < 0.05$) compared to treatment A, B and D. The highest body length was reached by treatment B (47.0 ± 4.58 mm), followed A (44.0 ± 5.00 mm), D (41.7 ± 10.41 mm) and C (33.0 ± 3.46 mm). Optimum total body length was obtained in probiotic application started at 5 days after stocking but no significant difference in specific and daily growth rate among the treatments.

KEYWORDS: probiotic application, period, *Pangasius djambal*, larvae, growth

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INTRODUCTION

Aquaculture has become an important economic activity in many countries. In large-scale production facilities, where aquatic animals are exposed to stressful conditions, problems related to diseases and deterioration of environmental conditions often occur and result in serious economic losses. The increase of productivity in aquaculture has been accompanied by ecological impacts including emergence of a large variety of pathogens and bacterial resistance (Balcazar, 2006). The immunostimulatory effect of probiotics has been established in many systems including fish (Nayak *et al.*, 2007).

The development of non-antibiotic and environment friendly agents is one of the key factors for health management in aquaculture (Qi *et al.*, 2009). The research of probiotics for aquatic animals is increasing with the demand for environment-friendly aquaculture. Some commercial products are referred to as probiotics, though they were designed to treat the rearing medium, not to supplement the diet. The probiotic treatments may be considered as methods of biological control, the so-called "biocontrol" that termed the limitation of pests by the introduction of adverse organism, like parasites or specific pathogens (Gatesoupe, 1999). Balcazar *et al.*, (2006) reported that in aquaculture, probiotics have been used to control diseases, enhance specific and non-specific immunity, provide nutrients and enzymatic functions, and improve water quality. This statement concurred with Wang *et al.*, (2008) the probiotics prepared with microorganisms have important roles in pond culture, particularly with respect to productivity, the nutrition of the cultured animals, disease control, water quality, and environmental impact of the effluent. Kesarcodi-Watson *et al.*, (2008) theorized that the probiotic should not be harmful to the host it desired for and it should be accepted by the host, e.g. through ingestion and

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potential colonization and replication within the host. It should reach the location where the effect is required to take place.

Catfishes of the family Pangasiidae are of great economic importance in Indonesia. Among these pangasiids, *Pangasius djambal* Bleeker reaches large size (more than 20 kg individual body weight) and is one of the fish species most appreciated by consumers in Sumatra and other Indonesian areas (Legendre *et al.*, 2000). Not only the price and consumers, but also because of the biological aspects such as large size per individual and omnivorous (Arifin, 1990).

Pangasiidae are economically important riverine catfishes generally occurring in freshwater from the Indian Subcontinent to the Indonesian Archipelago. *Pangasius djambal* is presently known from most major drainage of Sumatra, in the Musi, Batang Hari, and Indragiri Rivers. The species also occurs in Java, respectively, in the Brantas and Solo Rivers, in Kalimantan, in The Barito, Mendawai, and Kahayan Rivers (Gustiano, 2009). In a recent paper by Legendre *et al.*, (2000) the larvae of *P. djambal* were bigger than those of *P. hypophthalmus* and they were easier to cultivate and high survival and growth rate.

Target production of *Pangasius* in 2011 amounted to 383 MT will be increased to 651 thousand tones for the coming year. In a recent, the patin super quality requirements at least 100 tons per month, which is supplied to restaurants and five-star hotel. But this product is still by imported. Biggest catfish production still dominated by Vietnam (KKP, 2012). The one thing to increased production can be obtained from application of probiotic in larvae rearing.

Research in probiotics for aquaculture at an early stage of development is still needed. Experiment has mainly been conducted with fish larvae, where significant reductions in mortality have been obtained (Gomez-Gil *et al.*, 2000). Increasing the production can be achieved if environmental conditions supported during rearing period. The increased production was done in two stages, seeding stage and cultivation stage (Hardjamulia *et al.*, 1986). The good adaptation of this species to pond environment, as well as its resistance to handling, high growth rate and ability to become sexually mature in captivity, confirm its great potential for aquaculture. However, up to now its culture has not been possible due to lack of fry (Legendre *et al.*, 2000). At present, data about optimum period for probiotic application in rearing of *Pangasius djambal* larvae are still lacking. The principal objective of this study was to know effect of different period for probiotic application on growth performance of Asian catfish *Pangasius djambal* larvae.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Design

Two hundred and eighty larvae averaging 4.7 ± 0.126 mm of initial total body length were stocked in each aquarium. The size of each aquarium was $95 \times 45 \times 45$ cm³ filled with 100 liters of water and 0.003 mg/L of commercial probiotic. Sampling were taken every 7 days and the experiment was conducted for 35 days. The treatments consisted of three probiotic application at (A) probiotic application started at 3 days after stocking; (B) probiotic application started at 5 days after stocking; (C) probiotic application started at 7 days after stocking; and (D) without any probiotic application as control, and all treatments were repeated in triplicate. At the start of age 2 to 7 days larvae were fed by *Artemia* nauplii every 3 hours (eight times per day). Followed feeding by *Tubifex* worms (*Tubifex tubifex*) at 8 to 15 days, then fed by commercial pellets with doses 3% of total biomass per day at age 16 to 35 days.

The sampling was done every 7 days during experiment. The larvae was reared in the aquarium for 35 days. Larvae randomly sampled per aquarium with the determined parameters were Total Body Length (TL), Specific Growth Rate (SGR), and Daily Growth Rate (DGR). The body length of the fish was measured at the beginning and the final of the trial and specific growth rate was calculated as: $SGR = (LnLt - LnLo) \times 100\% / t - to$, where *Lt* and *Lo* are the final and initial average total body length (mm) of the fish and *t - to* is the duration (days) between samplings (Hardjamulia *et al.*, 1986). While, Akinwale & Faturoti (2007) daily growth rate was

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calculated as: $DGR = (Lt - Lo)/t$, where Lt and Lo are the final and initial average total body length (mm) and t is the duration (days). Water quality measurement included temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO), and hydrogen-ion concentration (pH). Temperature was recorded daily, dissolved oxygen and pH was controlled each week.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical test was performed using SPSS statistical software. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the significant ($P < 0.05$) difference between the tested groups, followed by a multiple range test (Duncan New Multiple Range test). Data were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard error.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Growth Performance

Growth performance of each treatments for 35 days rearing period in this experiment shown in Table 1. At the end of the experiment, the final body length of treatment C (probiotic application started at 7 days after stocking) showed significant difference ($P < 0.05$) compared to treatment A (probiotic application started at 3 days after stocking), B (probiotic application started at 5 days after stocking) and D (without any probiotic application/control). The highest final TL was reached by treatment B (47.0 ± 4.58 mm), then A (44.0 ± 5.00 mm), D (41.7 ± 10.41 mm) and C (33.0 ± 3.46 mm). Highest increased in total body length of larvae was obtained on probiotic application started at 5 days after stocking which was increased up to 100%. The average of total body length in every sampling is presented on Fig. 1. On the first sampling, it has not clearly seen the different between the treatment effects. On the second until fifth sampling (5 weeks), the growth difference on the four treatments were seen. The pattern showed the improvement during the rearing period. These four treatments showed similar patterns of growth during 35 days rearing period. Treatment B showed a relatively higher growth compared treatment A, D and treatment C. Growth in total body length of *Pangasius djambal* larvae tended to increase each weeks in all treatments. Thus, maximum TL reached in treatment probiotic application started at 3 days after stocking (47.0 ± 4.58 mm) higher than Baras *et al.*, (2010) *Pangasius djambal* larvae attained 44.2 ± 5.50 mm TL at 35 day after hatching. It showed that the addition of probiotics to the aquaria in different periods affected to the growth performance of *Pangasius djambal* larvae.

Fig. 1. Average total body length (cm ind.⁻¹).

No significant difference was found in specific growth rate among the four treatments ($P > 0.05$). SGR of probiotic application started at 5 days after stocking was higher than probiotic application started at 3 days after stocking, 7 days after stocking and without probiotic application (Fig. 2). Specific growth rate in all treatment showed patterns decreased up to a week-5 with the highest value in treatment B and treatment A, followed by treatments D and lowest in treatment C (probiotic application started at 7 days after stocking).

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Fig. 2. Specific growth rate of *Pangasius djambal* larvae (% day⁻¹).

Mean values of daily growth rate at different periods for probiotic application were not significantly difference ($P > 0.05$). DGR was shown in Fig. 3 with the pattern of rising up in 14 days for treatment A and decreased for treatment B, C and D (control). Treatment A, B and D tends to declined until day-28 and increased again until day-35. While on treatment C (probiotic application started at 7 days after stocking) showed that daily growth rate decreased to 35 days. Similarly with other observation that growth rate of milkfish (Tangko *et al.*, 2007), *Penaeus semisulcatus* (Wardana *et al.*, 2006) and *Penaeus monodon* (Gunarto *et al.*, 2006) used probiotic application tended higher than control (without probiotic).

Probiotic application started at 7 days after stocking cause lower growth than early probiotic application on larvae rearing. This cause of efficiency of feed utilization is not optimal. Early time in probiotic addition for larvae rearing obtained the better growth on good environmental rearing, while probiotic can helps food retention in digestive system. Result of this experiment was similar on the experiments in others species were carried out to evaluate of growth performance by probiotic addition. Jusadi *et al.*, (2004) stated that growth rate, food conversion ratios, protein retention and lipid retention of *Pangasius hypophthalmus* improved by probiotic used. It also reported Wang *et al.*, (2008) that the addition of probiotic could increase the growth performance of tilapias, *O. niloticus*.

Supplementation of trout starter diet with the proper density of commercial *Bacillus* probiotic could be beneficial for growth and survival of rainbow trout fry, especially in fast growing conditions, where it would be essential to stimulate the precocious maturation of digestive system (Wache *et al.*, 2006) (Bagheri *et al.*, 2008). Mortazavi-Tabrizi *et al.*, (2008); El-Ashram *et al.*, (2008) evaluated the effects of different levels of yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (0.05%, 0.1%, 0.15%, and 0.2%) as growth promoters of rainbow trout. They found that, specific growth rate and feed conversion rate were significantly ($P < 0.05$) different among treatment groups, also SGR were higher compared to the control.

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Fig. 3. Daily growth rate of *Pangasius djambal* larvae (mm day⁻¹).

Table 1. Growth performance of *Pangasius djambal* in each treatment during for 35 days of culture

Variable	Probiotic time (day)			
	3	5	7	0
Rearing period (days)	35	35	35	35
Initial total body length (mm ind. ⁻¹)	4.7 ± 0.126	4.7 ± 0.126	4.7 ± 0.126	4.7 ± 0.126
Final total body length (mm ind. ⁻¹)	44.0 ± 5.00 ^{ab}	47.0 ± 4.58 ^b	33.0 ± 3.46 ^a	41.7 ± 10.41 ^{ab}
Specific growth rate (%day ⁻¹)	6.38 ± 0.33 ^a	6.57 ± 0.28 ^a	5.56 ± 0.29 ^a	6.17 ± 0.77 ^a
Daily growth rate (mm day ⁻¹)	11.23 ± 1.43 ^a	12.09 ± 1.31 ^a	8.09 ± 0.99 ^a	10.56 ± 2.97 ^a

Values followed by different superscripts in the same row are significantly different (P<0.05).

Uniformity rate of larva rearing for probiotic application were lower than without probiotic application. This cause of good environment treatment by probiotic application.

Water Quality

Fish are dependent on both internal and external (ecological) factors, which control or synchronize many activities or functions, including growth capacity. It is possible to classify such ecological factors into two types: (1) determining factors (temperature, probiotic time, photoperiod) which act directly through receptors to increase or decrease growth; and (2) limiting factors, which operate above (ammonia) or below (oxygen) a specific threshold or within a tolerance range (pH) (Boeuf and Payan, 2001). Observation by Wang *et al.*, (2008) found that the stability of probiotics is influenced by various factors, including the species, strain biotype, water activity, temperature, hydrogen-ion concentration (pH), osmotic pressure, mechanical friction and oxygen. Gomez-Gil *et al.*, (2000) also suggested it is important to provide larvae with a healthy environment that includes a beneficial microbial community.

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Parameters of water quality as an important factor in the cultivation were observed during rearing period. The result indicated that water quality was still in decent condition for the life of *Pangasius djambal* larvae as shown in Table 2. Feed excess or faeces was removed by siphoning everyday to maintain water quality media remains in optimal condition. This was done by Boyd (1990) that on the nutrients budget in intensive and semi-intensive fish culture ponds, that large quantity of feed is not utilized by fish and often accumulated in pond.

Table 2. Water quality data during rearing period of *Pangasius djambal* larvae.

Parameters	Results
Temperature (°C)	28.5–29.5
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	1.91–1.99
pH	7.7–8.5

Temperature during rearing period of *Pangasius djambal* larvae was also stable with a range of 28.5–29.5°C. In general, the concentration of dissolved oxygen ranged between 1.91 and 1.99 mg/L. As with the other water quality variables, pH was relatively stable, that is about 7.7–8.5. A study by Hung *et al.*, (2004) in aquaria, the suitable water temperature ranged from 28 to 30°C with pH between 7.0 and 8.0. While According to Ferdoushi and Haque (2006), the values of temperature and pH were 30.06–30.13°C and 7.12–9.1. This condition was supported by Legendre *et al.*, (2000) some environmental parameters tolerated by *Pangasius djambal* for oxygen concentration ranged > 3 mg/L for eggs and larvae stage and between 0.6–9.6 mg/L for fingerlings and broodstock, pH between 6.0–8.9 and temperature between 27.0–31.0°C.

CONCLUSION

Optimum total body length of *Pangasius djambal* larvae was obtained in addition of probiotic application started at days 5th after stocking. While, specific and daily growth rate showed no significant difference between the treatments.

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